

UNIVERSITY OF WARWICK

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

In 2018-2019, there were 165 higher education institutions (HEIs) in the UK. A report on a survey by Universities UK (UUK)¹ in 2019 found that 81% of HEIs had recently provided improved support for student reporting. In June 2021, campaign group 'Reclaim the Campus'² published a report examining policies on sexual harassment at 40 UK universities, finding that only 13 of the universities had specific sexual misconduct policies. As there is no current legislation focused on GBV for the higher education (HE) sector, a voluntary approach is in place for institutions to implement guidance in the form of policies and recommendations for change.

The Equality Act 2010 drove the implementation of some policies for people with 'protected characteristics', which include sex, sexual orientation, and gender reassignment. More recently, the Office for Students (OfS) (the regulator for HE in England) published a 'Statement of Expectations',³ which is designed to provide a 'set of consistent recommendations to support higher education providers ... to prevent and respond to incidents of harassment and sexual misconduct'. This Statement is not monitored or requiring of registration, and the OfS cannot intervene or provide resolution or redress related to individual student cases and complaints (which must be dealt with through universities' internal complaints and disciplinary procedures) or constitute a regulatory requirement. Nevertheless, this Statement is a cause for institutional change. Though there have been reviews of individual universities following highly publicised sexual misconduct cases, no sanctions have been imposed and there is no oversight of the implementation of recommended change.

¹ <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/topics/equality-diversity-and-inclusion/survey-demonstrates-positive-university>

² <https://www.reclaimthecampus.com/the-reclaim-report>

³ <https://www.officeforstudents.org.uk/advice-and-guidance/student-wellbeing-and-protection/prevent-and-address-harassment-and-sexual-misconduct/statement-of-expectations/>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The University of Warwick has a number of policies that are specifically related to sexual misconduct and others that are more general. The set of **seven policies** are:

- University of Warwick Principles
- Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Policy (*in the process of being replaced with a new Social Inclusion Policy*)
- Dignity at Warwick Policy
- Student Sexual Misconduct Policy
- Student Complaints Resolution Procedure
- Staff Sexual Misconduct Policy and Procedure
- Regulation 23 Student Disciplinary Offences

A broad range of actors and stakeholders are identified as involved in equality and diversity work, including the Social Inclusion Committee, departmental equality, diversity and inclusion representatives, task forces on gender, race and LGBTQIA+ issues and a disabled staff network group. University of Warwick has also included gender identity which, although not mentioned in the Equality Act, is used as best practice following feedback from the LGBTQIA+ community.

[Report + Support - University of Warwick](#) was introduced in 2019 where staff and students can report with their name or anonymously sexual misconduct, discrimination, bullying and harassment and hate incidents and hate crimes. Annual reports are published, most recently the '[Report and Support Annual Report 2020-21](#)'. There is a website section at the Report + Support dedicated to [sexual misconduct](#) which sets out what sexual misconduct is (including online), provides advice and guidance if someone has experienced sexual misconduct, and provides advice and guidance for those that have witnessed it. The site also provides a place for all parts of the university to highlight work and [campaigns](#) including individual campaigns such as during Sexual Abuse and Sexual awareness Week 2022 and ongoing campaigns such as those run by the Student's Union e.g. #WEGetConsent, and external campaigns e.g. Ask for Angela.

The University also provides an on campus Sexual and Domestic Abuse Adviser.

URLs

- › the Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Policy:
https://livewarwickac.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/human_resources/_layouts/15/WopiFrame.aspx?guestaccesstoken=0QM%2b5B%2b54IJJPxIqGkcH1EHnWxpHR96bn6KTdWUbdg%3d&docid=061b844357e2a4914b922562a0206c3c3&action=default&cid=b180809b-cda2-4a8c-a9e0-bbda777d46e0
- › The Student Sexual Misconduct Policy:
https://warwick.ac.uk/about/values/sexual_misconduct/policy_and_procedure
- › Student Complaints Resolution Procedure:
https://warwick.ac.uk/services/feedbackcomplaints/students/complaints/student_complaints_resolution_procedure_as_at_30_september_2019.pdf
- › Regulation 23 Student Disciplinary Offences:
<https://warwick.ac.uk/services/gov/calendar/section2/regulations/disciplinary/>
- › The University of Warwick Principles
<https://warwick.ac.uk/about/values/>
- › The Dignity at Warwick policy and the Staff Sexual Misconduct Policy and Procedure, are only accessible via intranet.

Entry into force: Dignity at Work Policy entered into force in 2014, the EDI Policy in 2016. The Student Sexual Misconduct Policy was issued in 2019 and the Staff Sexual Misconduct Policy in 2021. The University of Warwick Principles were last revised in July 2020 and the Regulation 23 was amended in July 2022.

TRAINING

The Dignity at Warwick Policy states that the University will be responsible for providing awareness/training on this policy on a regular basis, which includes training staff as 'dignity contacts' on policy and relevant legislation. All students and staff are currently required to do the relevant Warwick Values Moodle every year. The Moodle communicates staff and student's rights and responsibilities as members of the Warwick community that enable the University to create a working, living and learning environment:

- Where everyone feels welcomed and safe to be themselves.
- Where everyone is treated with dignity and respect.
- Where there is equal opportunity for all to reach their potential.

There are also opportunities for individuals to be proactive, with training initiatives including an 'Active Bystander Initiative'⁴ as part of a community values programme that is scheduled into the timetable of first year students, with access to the pioneering film 'The Bystander Moment'⁵. This training, provided by the University, is also rolled out through the Warwick Students Union⁶, which also give access to a range of initiatives related to #WeGetConsent including collecting pledges, providing an educational blog⁷, and campaigning for safer nights out.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

- Dedicated teaching in this area including module "SO261-15 Gender and Violence" which is available to a range of undergraduate degree programmes as detailed in the module catalogue: <https://courses.warwick.ac.uk/modules/2021/SO261-15>.
- Dedicated research in this area, with gender-based violence being an explicit area of focus in the Centre for the Study of Women and Gender: <https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/soc/sociology/research/gender/>.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The policies mapped cover the following **seven** forms of violence: physical violence, psychological violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, organisational violence and online violence. While all policies address sexual harassment, all the policies except the Student Sexual Misconduct Policy also address gender-based harassment. The Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Policy (which is being replaced with a

⁴ <https://warwick.ac.uk/services/dean-of-students-office/community-values-education/activebystanderintervention>

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https://encore.lib.warwick.ac.uk/iii/encore/record/C_Rb3685834_Sbystandermoment_Orightresult_U_X6?lang=eng&suite=cobalt&ivts=ozN0TvJQA9DGo9bWWt0lsA%3D%3D&casts=XuxTmK5LeL7Wm0qj7NpIng%3D%3D

⁶ <https://www.warwicksu.com/campaigns-communities/campaigns/active/welfare/consent/#newsUpdates>

⁷ <https://www.warwicksu.com/news/article/campaign/WeGetConsent-You-Said-We-Did/>

new Social Inclusion Policy) focused on the two forms of harassment. The two other policies address physical, psychological, sexual and online violence.

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The policies mapped combined cover all **7Ps**. The EDI policy focuses on 2Ps: prevention and protection, while the Student Sexual Misconduct and the Dignity at Warwick Policies both address prevention, protection, prosecution, and provision of services. The Student Sexual Misconduct Policy is the only policy that addresses prevalence, and the Dignity at Warwick Policy is the only one that addresses partnership. Policy is addressed in the Student Sexual Misconduct policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups: The seven policies combined address all target groups, which are **academic staff, non-academic staff and students**. The EDI and the Dignity at Warwick address all target groups while the Student Sexual Misconduct Policy focuses on students and the Staff Sexual Misconduct policy focuses on staff.

They also address **other** groups such as visitors, students with visiting student status, distance learners and individuals undertaking degree apprenticeships, or contractors.

Specific vulnerable groups: The policies mapped address the following **eight** groups as vulnerable to GBV: staff and students with disabilities, staff and students with migrant and ethnic minority backgrounds, LGBTQUIA+ staff and students, and new and expecting mothers. Both the EDI Policy and the Dignity at Warwick

Policy address all eight vulnerable groups. The three documents specifically mention everyone who is covered by the 'protected characteristics' of the Equality Act (2010). The purpose of the policy is to promote equality and fairness, and not to discriminate on the grounds of age, disability, gender reassignment, marriage and civil partnership, pregnancy, maternity, race, religion or belief, and sex or sexual orientation.

Intersectionality addressed: The University of Warwick Principles recognise multiple forms of discrimination that are not to be tolerated, and defines the right of everyone to be treated with respect regardless of their status, rank, grade, belief or any protected characteristic. The Report and Support page recognises the international nature of discrimination and inequality and enables reporting cases of harassment on the grounds of not only sex, sexual orientation, and gender reassignment but also age, disability, race and religion or belief.

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The Dignity at Warwick Policy addresses bystanders, stating that: anyone who has witnessed an event must be named when a formal complaint about bullying or harassment is made; also, the University regards anyone who has witnessed harassment or bullying and who was not the subject of it but was offended by it, to be deserving of protection.⁸

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The Dignity in Warwick policy explicitly addresses perpetrators, in the context that those being subjected to harassment or bullying are offered informal options to address their concerns with offenders.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: Yes. Until now the EDI Policy was the only document to set out a monitoring process through the monitoring of incidents. Now, the university is using Report and Support for disclosures and complaints, with quantitative information about number of cases and outcomes for students and staff in the annual published report⁹.

Evaluation: Yes, this is incorporated into the Report and Support annual report, see above link and also Student Discipline and Resolution¹⁰.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

There are separate procedures for staff and students.

[Report + Support - University of Warwick](#) was introduced in 2019 where staff and students can report with their name or anonymously sexual misconduct, discrimination, bullying and harassment and hate incidents and hate crimes.

For **staff**, the main procedure in relation to GBV, is the Dignity at Warwick Policy, which sets out a step-by-step procedure for reporting and investigation. It is currently being revised, as it has been replaced by Report + Support.

The policies define: Who to contact, how to report, describes the investigation procedure, a timeframe, responsible persons/units and outcomes.

⁸ See section Training.

⁹ Report and Support 2020-21 by Jemma Ansell: <https://prezi.com/i/view/uz9wTiyyOGMjTATHCq8F>

¹⁰ https://warwick.ac.uk/students/news/stay_safe_hub/safety_and_wellbeing/annual_report/

Who to contact: Staff are encouraged, where possible, to raise issues with the relevant individual(s) informally before the situation escalates. The University encourages constructive discussion of different views and approaches.

For staff concerned about the way they are being treated at work or in a work-related context, either by an individual or a group, they may wish to seek advice or help in the following ways (in addition to Report + Support):

- They can seek support or advice from a friend, a work colleague or trade union representative.
- They may contact the Counselling Service.
- They may speak to a member of staff who has been trained to help in this type of situation.
- Alternatively, they can complete the Online Reporting Form anonymously at <https://www2.warwick.ac.uk/services/equalops/dignityatwarwick/report/>
- If they opt for an informal route, this will not prejudice their right to submit a formal complaint at a later stage. The University recognises that it is not always appropriate to use the informal procedure, e.g. a serious sexual assault. Possible informal options to address their concerns include:
 - Making it clear to the person or persons causing the offence that their behaviour is unacceptable. If the offender is a third party or contractor, the Head of Department (or other appropriate manager) should also be informed. Another option could be to write directly to the person causing the offence explaining why their behaviour is offensive.
 - Contacting the Counselling Service or speaking to a member of staff who has been trained to help in this type of situation. A number of staff trained as 'Dignity Contacts' are available.
 - If the alleged harassment and/or bullying is occurring within a team, people may wish to speak to their team leader or other appropriate line manager.
 - Completing the Online Reporting Form anonymously – with the caution that in the case of anonymous reporting, it will not be possible to offer direct advice or begin a complaint process.
 - Speaking to HR Advisor.

How to report: If the behaviour persists following an approach, or if such an approach is not possible, people are advised to begin to take a note of the date and details of any relevant incidents that are distressing, including a note of the impact the incidents. If the issue is not resolved by an informal approach, the matter can be raised formally in accordance with the Grievance Policy.

In bringing a formal complaint of harassment/bullying, the complainant will need to provide:

- The name of the person whose conduct is considered to amount to harassment or bullying
- The type of conduct that is causing offence, together with specific examples if possible
- Dates and times when incidents of harassment or bullying occurred, and where they occurred
- The names of any staff or other students who witnessed any incidents, or who themselves may have been the victims of harassment or bullying by the same person
- Any action that the person has already taken to try to deal with the issues raised.

Description of investigation: During the process of dealing with the grievance, the head of department (or an appointed representative) should take appropriate and reasonable steps to minimise and/or supervise any contact between the relevant parties and to keep them informed of these steps at all times. The University reserves the right to suspend any member of staff on normal full pay during any investigation process to protect individuals (suspension on normal full pay is not a disciplinary sanction).

Every safeguard must be made against the possibility of recrimination or victimisation, particularly in cases where a grievance is upheld. The head of department (or an appointed representative) has a duty to monitor the longer-term situation as far as possible, both in terms of day to day working relations within the department and in the wider community. No further action may be taken if the claim(s) of harassment are not upheld. However, if there is a continuing working relationship between the two parties, the head of department must ensure that appropriate steps are taken to help to restore a reasonable working relationship between the parties.

Responsible persons/units: The head of department (or nominated representative)

Outcomes: Where the allegation(s) of harassment have been upheld, relevant actions in line with the University's disciplinary procedures may be implemented.

For students, there is the **Student Complaints Resolution Procedure** in addition to the Report + Support. The complaint may relate to, among others, inappropriate behaviour or treatment by a staff member, student or individual associated with the University (including contravening the University's Dignity at Warwick Policy).

Who to contact: If a student complains to the University about the service of another organisation, the individual will be advised to contact the appropriate organisation directly. Where a complaint relates to a University service provided by another organisation, the complaint will be handled through the Student Complaints Resolution Procedure in liaison with the partner organisation.¹¹

How to report: Complaints should be raised with the most relevant service area or member of staff. To make a complaint, students must start with local resolution (Stage 1, see below) unless there are truly exceptional circumstances. Should a complaint include serious allegations of misconduct against another individual or individuals, it may be that the relevant staff or student disciplinary process may need to be used for investigation or determination of the outcome in conjunction with this Procedure.

Description of investigation: The Student Complaints Resolution Procedure has three levels:

Stage 1: Frontline / Local Resolution Early resolution of the complaint should be sought and it is expected that the vast majority of complaints will be resolved at Stage 1.¹²

The initial stage in the complaints procedure allows for straightforward complaints to be resolved quickly and effectively at the point at which the issue occurred. Once an outcome has been provided at Local Resolution Stage (e.g. through a facilitated discussion), a complainant or their representative has 10 working days to escalate their complaint to Stage 2 for a Formal Departmental Investigation and Resolution, together with supporting evidence, should the complaint or elements of it not be satisfactorily resolved at Stage 1.

¹¹ <https://warwick.ac.uk/services/feedbackcomplaints/students/complaints/procedure/section6>

¹² <http://www2.warwick.ac.uk/services/feedbackcomplaints/students/complaints/stage1/>

Stage 2: Formal Departmental Investigation and Resolution¹³

The second stage of the complaints procedure may be used if the complainant is not satisfied with attempts to informally resolve their complaint. Alternatively, this stage can be used if the complaint is so complex or serious that informal resolution would be inappropriate. Following the communication of the written outcome from the formal Stage 2 Departmental Investigation and Resolution Stage, the student or their representative has 10 University working days to escalate their complaint to Stage 3 for Formal Institutional Review and Final Resolution, stating the grounds on which a review is requested.

Stage 3: Formal Institutional Review and Final Resolution¹⁴

If the complainant is not satisfied with the Stage 2 outcome then, if they meet the published criteria, they can apply for a review of the Stage 2 process to include previously unavailable evidence or determine that appropriate processes were followed and that the Stage 2 decision was reasonable.

Timeframe: The complaint shall be made as soon as possible, the latest within three months of the problem becoming apparent. The appeal for stages 2 and 3 needs to be made within 10 working days.

Responsible persons/units: For stage 3, these are: Wellbeing Support Services, including the Disability Services team, the Mental Health team, the Counselling Service, the University's Dean of Students, departmental Personal Tutors, the Students' Union Advice Centre, and the Chaplaincy. Human Resources will be able to direct staff members to the appropriate support available.

Outcomes: Should any complaint not be resolved through this internal three stage process, students are able to request that their complaint be independently reviewed by the Office of the Independent Adjudicator (OIA), the HE sector ombudsman.

This document reflects the situation as of July 2022. Some of the sections of this vignette may only reflect on the initial three mapped policies (The Equality, Diversity and Inclusion policy, the Dignity at Warwick policy, the Student Sexual Misconduct Policy) carried out in 2021. Four additional policies have been added in 2022 during the vignette preparation.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Kate Clayton-Hathway in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

¹³ <http://www2.warwick.ac.uk/services/feedbackcomplaints/students/complaints/stage2/>

¹⁴ <http://www2.warwick.ac.uk/services/feedbackcomplaints/students/complaints/stage3/>

